

Recent Advances in the Chemistry of Simple and Bimetallic Alkoxides of Later Transition Elements (with particular reference to the '3d' series)*

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After giving a survey of the spurt in the literature during the last 4-5 years on the chemistry of later transition metals in general, a brief account has been presented of the recent work carried out in the author's laboratories on the simple and bimetallic alkoxides of later '3d' metals. The synthesis of a number of simple alkoxides of Cr(III and IV), Mn(II), Fe(II and III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) has been described. Except for alkoxides of iron(III), Fe(OR)₃ in general and Cr(OBu^t)₄, almost all these alkoxides are non-volatile and insoluble in organic solvents. These polymeric alkoxides of later '3d' metals further differ from the alkoxides of earlier transition and main group metals in comparatively much lesser lability of their alkoxy groups. The sharp differences (again observed for the first time in metal alkoxide chemistry) in the alcoholysis reactivity of these alkoxides with changes in ramification of the alkyl group have been correlated with changes in their stereochemistry. Further, a large number of monomeric volatile bimetallic isopropoxides of the above metals with the general formula M[Al(OPrⁱ)₄]_n, have been synthesised. Physico-chemical (spectroscopic and magnetic) properties of these derivatives indicate simple coordinated structures with tetraisopropoxyaluminate moieties functioning as bidentate and in some cases as tridentate ligands.

ALTHOUGH the alkoxide chemistry of non-transition and earlier transition elements has been extensively explored during the last three decades¹, the corresponding derivatives of later transition metals received very little attention¹⁻³ till recently except for some work on the magnetic and spectroscopic properties of mainly the methoxide derivatives of '3d'⁸⁻⁹ metals⁴. Further, in contrast to the soluble and volatile alkoxides of earlier transition metals, almost all the alkoxides of later '3d' elements were found to be insoluble with the exception of iron(III) alkoxides⁵ and chromium tetra-*t*-butoxides⁶. There appears to be a spurt, particularly during the last 4-5 years, in research activity in a number of laboratories on the alkoxy derivatives of later elements of the first transition series (chromium⁷⁻¹¹, manganese¹²⁻¹⁴, cobalt^{15,16}, nickel^{17,18} and copper¹⁹⁻²⁵) and of the second and third transition series (molybdenum^{24,25}, tungsten²⁶, rhenium^{27,28}, ruthenium²⁹, rhodium³⁰ and platinum³¹⁻³⁵) including the synthesis of a number of soluble bimetallic^{36,37} alkoxides of later '3d' metals. Sterically demanding alcohols have also received special attention^{38,39} for enhancing the kinetic stability of transition metal alkoxides in general.

Recent work carried out in our laboratories on the synthesis, interchange reactions, spectroscopic and magnetic properties of the simple alkoxides with the general formulae Cr(OR)₃, Co(OR)₂, Ni(OR)₂ and Cu(OR)₂, as well as the bimetallic

alkoxides Cr[Al(OR)₄]₃, Mn[Al(OR)₄]₂, Fe[Al(OR)₄]₂ and Co[Al(OR)₄]₂ will now be briefly presented.

Special characteristics of alkoxides of later '3d' transition metals :

Lower alkoxides of earlier transition and main group elements (with the exception of methoxides) are generally volatile and soluble in organic solvents. By contrast, the alkoxides of later '3d' metals [with the exception of ferric and chromium(IV) alkoxides and some highly hindered alkoxides of bivalent chromium¹⁰ and manganese¹²] are non-volatile and insoluble in organic solvents.

Another novel feature of these new alkoxides is their selective reactivity towards other alcohols. In spite of the strength of the metal-oxygen bonds, one of the characteristic features of alkoxides of elements studied so far is their lability due to facile exchange of alkoxy groups - both intra-molecular, as in the case of aluminium isopropoxide⁴⁰, as well as inter-molecular. The latter type of exchange has, in fact, been utilised extensively in our as well as other laboratories for the synthesis of a wide variety of higher alkoxides and other interesting derivatives by treating lower alkoxides of different elements with higher alcohols and other hydroxy ligands like silanols⁴¹, glycols⁴², β-diketones⁴³⁻⁴⁵, β-ketoesters⁴⁴, alkanolamines⁴⁶, oximes, hydroxylamines⁴⁷ and Schiff bases⁴⁸ as well as with other reagents like organic esters⁴⁹, silyl esters⁵⁰, β-ketoamines,

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thiols, thio- β -diketones^{44,51}, acyl halides⁵², acid amides⁵³ and carboxylic acids as well as their anhydrides⁵⁴. The reactions of the new alkoxides of later '3d' metals have also been investigated with a number of hydroxy agents (alkanolamines, β -diketones and carboxylic acids).

Further, sharp variations have been noticed for the first time in the alcoholysis tendencies of Cr(III)⁷, Co(II)¹⁶ and Ni(II)¹⁸ alkoxides and these have been correlated with their varying stereochemical geometries depicting differences in thermodynamic stabilities depending on the nature of the alkyl or aryl group involved.

Alkoxides of chromium :

Methoxide and ethoxide of the most common oxidation state(III) of chromium were obtained by a novel method involving ultraviolet irradiation of tricarbonylarenechromium⁵⁵. Primary alkoxides of chromium(III) have been synthesised recently in our laboratories by the simple reactions of CrCl₃.3THF adduct (which is soluble in organic solvents) with lithium alkoxides :

(where R = Me, Et or Buⁿ)

Cr(OPr^t)₃ and Cr(OBu^t)₃ could not be prepared by this method; some hydrolysed products were obtained instead.

All the primary alkoxides of chromium are pale green polymeric solids insoluble in organic solvents. They do not undergo alcoholysis or transesterification reactions even under forcing conditions and hence Cr(OPr^t)₃ or Cr(OBu^t)₃ could not be synthesised even through these routes. Chromium(III) phenoxide could, however, be obtained by refluxing Cr(OEt)₃ with excess phenol in benzene, removing the ethanol produced azeotropically with the solvent. This Cr(OPh)₃ was found to undergo reaction with excess isopropanol (but not with tertiary butanol) and on repeating the treatment a number of times, almost pure Cr(OPrⁱ)₃ could be obtained as a green insoluble solid. It may be of some interest that we were finally successful in synthesising Cr(OBu^t)₃ by an alternative simpler route, i.e., the reaction of CrCl₃.3THF with three moles of LiOBu^t (in the absence of excess Bu^tOH) in THF itself :

Cr(OBu^t)₃, obtained as a soluble blue product in the above reaction, gave volatile Cr(OBu^t)₄, which could be distilled as a blue liquid under reduced pressure. The spectrum of this liquid shows bands at 15,700 cm⁻¹, 13,870 cm⁻¹ and a shoulder at 25,300 cm⁻¹, which can be understood on the basis of a tetrahedral environment for chromium in this compound⁵⁶. The special stability of the oxidation state(IV) for chromium in Cr(OBu^t)₄ also appears to be due to two singly occupied lower e_g shells.

Electronic spectra of chromium(III) alkoxides have been measured in the visible range in nujol mulls. The spectra are very similar and may be interpreted (Table 1) on the basis of an octahedral environment⁵⁶ for chromium(III).

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC VISIBLE SPECTRA OF CHROMIUM(III) ALKOXIDES

Product	⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (10Dq)	⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g}	B
Cr(OMe) ₃ ^a	17,610 cm ⁻¹	24,150 cm ⁻¹	612 cm ⁻¹
Cr(OEt) ₃ ^a	17,000 cm ⁻¹	23,470 cm ⁻¹	600 cm ⁻¹
Cr(OBu ⁿ) ₃ ^a	17,060 cm ⁻¹	23,700 cm ⁻¹	610 cm ⁻¹
Cr(OPh) ₃	16,900 cm ⁻¹	23,920 cm ⁻¹	615 cm ⁻¹
Cr(OMe) ₃	17,240 cm ⁻¹	23,800 cm ⁻¹	609 cm ⁻¹
Cr(OEt) ₃ ^b	16,370 cm ⁻¹	23,470 cm ⁻¹	654 cm ⁻¹
Cr(OPr ^t) ₃ ^b	15,880 cm ⁻¹	22,940 cm ⁻¹	720 cm ⁻¹
Cr(OMe) ₃ ^c	17,180 cm ⁻¹	24,150 cm ⁻¹	613 cm ⁻¹
Cr(OPr ^t) ₃ ^c	16,180 cm ⁻¹	23,280 cm ⁻¹	728 cm ⁻¹

(a) Prepared from LiOR method; (b) Prepared from Cr(OPh)₃; (c) Prepared from Cr(OBu^t)₃.

The special inertness of Cr(III) alkoxides in alcoholysis reactions can be understood in the light of the stability of octahedral chromium(III), in which each of the three low energy t_{2g} orbitals are occupied singly; the Jahn-Teller effect does not appear to be effectively operative in disturbing the regularity of this octahedral species. Cr(III) derivatives in octahedral environment, therefore, do not tend to undergo substitution reactions both by the dissociation (S_N¹) as well as associative (S_N²) mechanisms.

Although Cr(III) primary alkoxides do not undergo alcoholysis reactions, Cr(OPr^t)₃ could be converted into Cr(OMe)₃ or Cr(OEt)₃ by refluxing with excess MeOH or EtOH. Cr(OPr^t)₃ does not, however, undergo alcoholysis reactions with tertiary or other secondary alcohols even under forcing conditions. On treatment with MeOH, EtOH or Pr^tOH, Cr(OBu^t)₃ readily gave the corresponding Cr(III) alkoxides, which is easily understood on the basis of greater stability of the octahedral species.

In view of the general inertness of primary alkoxides of chromium(III), a more detailed study of their substitution reactions was carried out. Although inert to other alcohols, they undergo interchange with chelating ligands like ethanolamine, β -diketones and carboxylic acids. A very wide variety of derivatives synthesised in such reactions have been characterised by their detailed spectral and magnetochemical studies⁷ :

[N.B. The above reactions are slow and yield products which are insoluble in organic solvents.]

[where R=Me or Et; $\beta\text{-dkH}$ =acetylacetone (acacH), benzoylacetone (bzacH) or 2-theonyltrifluoroacetone (ttaH); and $x=1, 2$ or 3]

[N.B. These reactions with β -diketones are slow in the first stage, but become more facile with the formation of soluble derivatives. Products $\text{Cr(OR)}_s(\beta\text{-dk})$ are polymeric and $\text{Cr(OR)}(\beta\text{-dk})_2$ are dimeric with chromium atoms in octahedral environment.]

[N.B. In spite of their solubility, these mixed ethoxide β -diketonates also do not undergo alcoholysis with higher alcohols, but react readily with other chelating β -diketone ligands.]

Reactions of chromium alkoxides with carboxylic acids can be represented by the following equation :

(where R= CH_3 or C_2H_5 and R'= C_7H_{15} , $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{27}$, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}$ or $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{43}$)

[N.B. Reactions and products are similar to those with β -diketones; carboxylate moieties behave as bidentate ligands. Products can be recrystallized from benzene.]

Highly oxygen sensitive (pyrophoric) alkoxides of chromium(II) have been recently reported¹⁰ by alcoholysis of $\text{Cr}[\text{N}(\text{SiMe}_3)_2]_2 \cdot 2\text{LL}'$, where L, L' = ether, THF or py. All the normal Cr(II) alkoxides (ethoxide to pentyloxy) are yellow/orange except the methoxide which is purple; all secondary alkoxides are purple/violet and all the tertiary alkoxides are blue derivatives. Solubility of these alkoxides is influenced strongly by drying conditions. Sterically hindered alkoxides, e.g., chromium(II)-2,6-di-tertiary-butylphenoxide,

$\text{Cr}(\text{O} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{Bu}^t \\ \diagdown \text{Bu}^t \end{array})_2 \cdot (\text{THF})_2$, are less associated, depict higher solubility in general and tend to form crystalline adducts with donor ligands.

Alkoxides of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) :

Alkoxides of these metals have been prepared^{16,18} by the following reactions :

(where R=Me, Et or Pr^t)

[N.B. $\text{Co(OBu}^t)_2$ could not be prepared by this method.]

(where R=Me, Et, Prⁿ, Buⁿ, Hxⁿ, Pr^t, Bu^s, Bu^t, Am^t or Hex^t)

[N.B. Adducts $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot \text{ROH}$ formed by adding NiCl_2 to ROH are soluble in case of primary alcohols, but insoluble in secondary or tertiary alcohols. The reactions with LiOR in the latter two cases are facilitated by addition of a little pyridine due to its solubilising effect.]

(where R=Me, Et, Pr^t or Bu^t).

Out of the alkoxides of the above three metals, only Cu(II) alkoxides undergo facile alcohol interchange reactions similar to alkoxides of earlier transition metals :

(where R=Me, Et or Buⁿ and R'=Pr^t, Bu^s, Bu^t or Am^t)

Primary alkoxides of Co(II) and Ni(II), on the other hand, resemble those of Cr(III) in not undergoing interchange even under forcing conditions. Branched alkoxides of these metals, however, undergo facile interchange with primary alcohols even at room temperature. Extensive work has been carried out in our laboratories¹⁸ since 1977 on the exchange reactions of nickel alkoxides with alkanolamines, β -diketones and carboxylic acids, with results similar to those described above for chromium(III) alkoxides.

Visible spectra of all the above alkoxides have been recorded in Nujol mulls and throw light on their stereochemistry. Co(II) alkoxides (purple in colour) show a multiple band in the range $18235 \pm 285 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a shoulder on the higher frequency side in the range $20170 \pm 450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. These can be explained on the basis of the ν_3 transition, ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ which is characteristic for octahedral geometry of Co(II); these spectra are similar to those reported⁵⁷ for Co(OMe)₂.

Spectra of Ni(II) primary alkoxides (light green in colour) are characteristic of octahedral derivatives, which exhibit three well defined spin-allowed bands at $8750 \pm 250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [ν_1 ; ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}$]; $14810 \pm 115 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [ν_2 ; ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$] and $24980 \pm 125 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [ν_3 ; ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$]. The spectra of secondary and tertiary alkoxides (blue in colour) of Ni(II) clearly indicate a tetrahedral geometry with well defined spin-allowed transitions at $7580 \pm 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [ν_2 ; ${}^3\text{T}_1 \rightarrow {}^3\text{A}_2$] and $15850 \pm 70 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [ν_3 ; ${}^3\text{T}_1 \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_1(\text{P})$].

The magnetic moments of the primary alkoxides of nickel(II) fall in the range of 3.45 ± 0.04 B.M. and those of secondary as well as tertiary alkoxides are found in the range of 3.65 ± 0.05 B.M. at room temperature. These observations are in accord with their octahedral and tetrahedral configurations, respectively.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA*, g VALUES (est) AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF PRIMARY ALKOXIDES OF NICKEL(II)

Product	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (10 Dq)	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2)	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_1)	B	β	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	g
Ni(OMe) ₂	8500	14700	25100	900	0.86	3.49	2.22
Ni(OEt) ₂	8770	14490	25280	897	0.86	3.43	2.13
Ni(OPr ⁿ) ₂	9010	14600	24245	788	0.76	—	2.24
Ni(OBu ⁿ) ₂	9250	14750	23855	724	0.70	3.43	2.24
Ni(OHex ⁿ) ₂	9250	14925	24585	784	0.75	—	2.14
Ni(OOct ⁿ) ₂	9100	14815	24845	824	0.79	—	2.27

* Transitions and B in cm⁻¹.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA*, g VALUES (est) AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF SECONDARY AND TERTIARY ALKOXIDES OF NICKEL(II)

Product	1_G	${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ (ν_1)	${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3A_2$ (ν_2)	Dq	B	β	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	g
Ni(OPr ^t) ₂	22420 sh, 18657, 17065	15900	7550	409	870	0.84	3.65	2.22
Ni(OBu ^t) ₂	22472 sh, 18657, 17033	15790	7480	384	823	0.79	3.70	2.25
Ni(OBu ⁱ) ₂	22625 sh, 18618, 17007	15920	7680	395	827	0.79	3.61	2.23
Ni(OAm ^t) ₂	22522 sh, 18485, 16950	15850	7520	390	833	0.80	3.67	2.23

* Transitions, Dq and B in cm⁻¹.

TABLE 4—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF A FEW OTHER TYPICAL NICKEL(II) DERIVATIVES

Derivative	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (ν_1 ; 10 Dq)	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2)	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_1)	B	β
NiCl ₂ .MeOH	7937	13333	22400	795	0.74
NiCl ₂ .Pr ^t OH	7924	12903	21978	740	0.68
NiCl ₂ .Am ^t OH	7520	12195	21740	758	0.70
Ni(OMe)Cl*	7900	12900	22100	753	0.72
Ni(OMe)Cl.MeOH*	8100	13300	24000	866	0.83
Ni(OEt)Cl*	8000	13200	23610	854	0.82
Ni(OPr ^t)Cl*	8200	13100	22500	733	0.70
Ni(OMe)(OCH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂)@	9090	14390	23065	680	0.63
Ni(OPr ^t)(OCH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂)@	9090	14925	25562	881	0.82
Ni(OCH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂)@	9615	14925	23516	640	0.59
Ni(OMe)(acac) ^{oo}	8930	15528	24904	909	0.84
Ni(OPr ^t)(acac) ^{oo}	8970	14706	23098	726	0.67
Ni(OBu ^t)(acac) ^{oo}	9260	14860	24155	749	0.69
Ni(acac) ₂	8800	15267	25210	938	0.87
Ni(OMe)(OOC.C ₁₃ H ₂₇)†	8585	14620	24272	876	0.84
Ni(OPr ^t)(OOC.C ₁₃ H ₂₇)†	8695	14663	24155	849	0.81
Ni(OBu ^t)(OOC.C ₁₃ H ₂₇)†	8695	14577	23923	828	0.79
Ni(OOC.C ₁₃ H ₂₇) ₂ †	8930	15015	23520	784	0.75

* Soluble in parent alcohols and undergo alcoholysis reactions.

@ Insoluble in organic solvents and do not undergo alcoholysis reactions.

^{oo} Soluble in organic solvents in which it shows tetrameric association.

^{oo} Soluble in organic solvents in which they show trimeric association.

† Soluble in organic solvents; primary alkoxy derivatives do not undergo alcoholysis but secondary and tertiary alkoxy derivatives undergo alcoholysis.

The ligand field, (Dq), and Racah, (B), parameters for the tetrahedral secondary and tertiary alkoxydes of nickel (Table 3) were calculated by the method of Underhill and Billing^{5a}. As expected, the magnitude of 10 Dq values obtained in all the tetrahedral complexes are about four-ninth of the 10 Dq values observed (Table 2) for the corresponding octahedral compounds. The values of B in both octahedral and tetrahedral derivatives are found to be reduced below the free ion value (1041 cm⁻¹) showing an appreciable covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds in these alkoxydes derivatives.

At room temperature, all octahedral as well as tetrahedral nickel(II) alkoxydes give one signal in their electron spin resonance spectra in the polycrystalline state from which Lande splitting factors (g values) have been calculated to lie in the range 2.13-2.27 (Tables 2 and 3), indicating again a strong covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds in these complexes.

It may be interesting to record that the electronic spectra (Table 4) of a large number of allied derivatives of nickel(II), prepared by reactions represented for the sake of brevity by the

following equations, indicate an octahedral environment for nickel in all these cases (including those with ramified alkoxy ligand) :

(where $R = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, \text{C}_3\text{H}_7, \text{C}_4\text{H}_9, \text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}$ or C_8H_{17} and $x = 1-4$ at room temperature.)

$\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot \text{MeOH} + \text{R}'\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{NiCl}_2 \cdot \text{R}'\text{OH} + \text{MeOH} \uparrow$
 (where $\text{R}' = \text{C}_3\text{H}_7, \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$ or C_6H_{11} ; NiCl_2 does not dissolve or react with secondary and tertiary alcohols and the adducts could be prepared in these cases by alcohol interchange reactions only.)

(where $R = \text{CH}_3$ or C_3H_7)

(where $R = \text{CH}_3$ or C_3H_7 ;

$\text{R}' = \text{R}'' = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5, \text{CF}_3$ or $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{S}$)

(where $R = \text{CH}_3$ or C_3H_7 ; $\text{R}' = \text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{27}, \text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}$ or $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35}$).

A few mixed β -diketonates and carboxylates of nickel(II) could also be synthesised by the following types of reactions :

Nickel alkoxides undergo insertion reactions⁶⁰ also with substrates like isocyanates and these reactions can be represented as :

(where $R = \text{Me}$ or Pr^i ; $\text{R}' = \text{Ph}$ or naph ; $n = 1$ or 2).

All these reactions are exothermic in benzene and their completion was indicated by the disappearance of the band at $\sim 2250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (due to $-\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{O}$).

The appearance of an intense band at 1700 cm^{-1} (due to $\text{C}=\text{O}$) in the addition products suggests that the insertion has occurred at the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ site.

The spectra of the branched green alkoxides of copper, viz., $\text{Cu(OPr}^i)_2$, $\text{Cu(OBu}^n)_2$, $\text{Cu(OBu}^t)_2$ and $\text{Cu(OAm}^t)_2$ are characterised by broad absorptions in the visible range around $15200 \pm 635 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which generally tail deep into the near infrared region. This band can be assigned as a ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition, which is characteristic of Cu^{2+} in six coordinate tetragonal geometry. In addition to a sharper absorption in this region at $15500 \pm 70 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, another band appears around $19100 \pm 300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of blue primary alkoxides, Cu(OMe)_2 , Cu(OEt)_2 and $\text{Cu(OBu}^n)_2$ which indicates a distorted octahedral environment around copper(II) in these derivatives.

Magnetic susceptibilities of copper alkoxides show a lowering in the value with decrease in temperature [$\text{Cu(OAm}^t)_2$: 1.83 at 297° to 1.37 at 87°K ; $\text{Cu(OPr}^i)_2$: 1.50 at 297° to 0.98 at 88°K and $\text{Cu(OBu}^n)_2$: 1.18 at 299° to 0.64 at 88°K], which suggests antiferromagnetic exchange interaction between copper pairs in all these alkoxides, based on infinite chains⁶⁰ of methoxy bridged copper atoms rather than a layer type structure suggested earlier⁶¹. The values of exchange coupling constants (j) in these alkoxides have been calculated on the basis of Ising theory⁶² as 129, 81 and 43 cm^{-1} respectively for $\text{Cu(OBu}^n)_2$, $\text{Cu(OPr}^i)_2$ and $\text{Cu(OAm}^t)_2$.

Bimetallic alkoxides of chromium(III), manganese(II), iron(II and III), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) with aluminium :

Bimetallic isopropoxides of the above elements with aluminium have been prepared by the following reactions :

[where $n = 3$ for Fe(III) and $n = 2$ for Mn(II) , Fe(II) , Co(II) , Ni(II) or Cu(II)].

In view of the insolubility of CrCl_3 in organic solvents, its adduct $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{THF}$ was used as a starting material for a similar preparation of $\text{Cr[Al(OPr}^i)_4]_3$. All these reactions are exothermic. The products are coloured liquids/solids which are miscible/soluble in organic solvents and can be purified by distillation under reduced pressure. All of these depict monomeric behaviour in refluxing benzene.

These bimetallic isopropoxides react quantitatively with excess of ethanol, 2,2,2-trifluoroethanol and normal butanol to give the corresponding

derivatives which are also volatile and soluble in organic solvents :

The products, $M[Al(OMe)_4]_n$, obtained with excess methanol, however, are insoluble and non-volatile. The reactions with methanol were carried out in the case of $Cr[Al(OPr^t)_4]_3$ in 3:1 and 6:1 molar ratios also, yielding respectively $Cr[Al(OPr^t)_3(OMe)]_3$ and $Cr[Al(OPr^t)_2(OMe)_2]_3$; the former is soluble whereas the latter is only sparingly soluble in benzene.

Exchange reactions with excess tertiary alcohols, however, yielded interesting end products of the following types, $M[Al(OPr^t)(OBu^t)_3]_2$, $M[Al(OPr^t)_2(OAm^t)_2]_2$, $M[Al(OPr^t)_2(OBu^t)_2]_2$ and $M[Al(OPr^t)_2(OAm^t)_2]_2$. All these bimetallic derivatives could also be purified, unchanged, by distillation under reduced pressure and showed monomeric behaviour in refluxing benzene.

Isopropoxide acetylacetonate products, $M[Al(OPr^t)_{4-x}(acac)_x]_2$ or 3 (where $x=1$ or 2), obtained by treating the bimetallic isopropoxides with stoichiometric quantities of acetylacetonate have again been shown to be volatile monomeric products. Products of the types, $M[Al(OPr^t)_{4-x}(acac)_x]_2$ or 3 (where $x=3$ or 4) tended to dissociate

into metal isopropoxide or acetylacetonate and aluminium acetylacetonate.

The chemical reactions as well as spectroscopic and magnetic properties of the above interesting derivatives appear to indicate that most of these derivatives have structure (I) similar to those suggested earlier^{8,9}, but the data for a few cobalt, nickel and copper derivatives appear to be more easily understood on the basis of a structure of the type (II).

A similar conclusion has been reported by Stumpp and Hillebrand^{8,9} for products, $M[Al(OR)_4]_2$ ($M=Co, Ni$ or Cu ; $R=CH_3, C_2H_5, C_3H_7$ or C_4H_9) in a later publication.

The above tendency to attain octahedral geometry, for example, by $Ni[Al(OR)_4]_2$ derivatives, appears to increase as the alkoxy groups become smaller and less ramified. According to detailed

TABLE 5—BIMETALLIC ALKOXIDES AND ALLIED DERIVATIVES OF LATER '3d' TRANSITION METALS

Compound	Nature	Volatility (°C/...mm)	M.W. Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} (B.M./°K)	D_q (cm^{-1})
$Cr[Al(OPr^t)_4]_3$	Green viscous liquid	190/0.6	838 (842)	3.90/100	1527
$Mn[Al(OPr^t)_4]_3$	Brown viscous liquid	145/0.6	607 (582)	5.95/88 5.90/297	—
$Fe[Al(OPr^t)_4]_3$	Brown viscous liquid	130/0.8	1003 (846)	5.06/89 5.39/296	—
$Fe[Al(OPr^t)_4]_2$	Brown semi-solid	125/0.8	605 (582)	4.53/87 5.06/297	—
$Co[Al(OPr^t)_4]_2$	Purple liquid	140/0.6	629 (586)	4.62/92 4.39/297	873
$Ni[Al(OPr^t)_4]_2$	Pink liquid	120/0.6	570 (585)	3.29/90 3.39/294	823 (film) 895 (Pr^tOH) 912 (pyridine)
$Cu[Al(OPr^t)_4]_2$	Greenish blue liquid	135/0.6	604 (593)	1.22/87 1.64/297	1380
$Cr[Al(OPr^t)_3(OMe)]_3$	Lightgreen solid	215/0.8	—	3.84/300	1572
$Cr[Al(OPr^t)_2(OMe)_2]_3$	Green solid	255/0.8*	—	3.86/300	1582
$Cr[Al(OEt)_4]_3$	Green solid	235/0.8*	—	3.86/300	1577
$Cr[Al(OCH_2CF_3)_4]_3$	Brown viscous liquid	120/0.8*	1353 (1321)	3.86/300	1520
$Cr[Al(OPr^t)_3(acac)]_3$	Green pasty solid	140/0.8	967 (962)	3.82/300	1675
$Cr[Al(OPr^t)_2(acac)_2]_3$	Green solid	180/0.8*	1233 (1032)	3.83/300	1692
$Fe[Al(OPr^t)_2(OAm^t)_2]_3$	Brown solid	270/0.6*	976 (1014)	—	—
$Ni[Al(OPr^t)(OBu^t)_3]_2$	Purple solid	140/0.6*	691 (670)	3.14/88 3.47/300	736
$Ni[Al(OPr^t)_2(acac)_2]_2$	Brown pinkish solid	240/0.6*	708 (745)	3.28/300	769
$Cu[Al(OCH_2CF_3)_4]_2$	Blue semi-solid	115/0.5	—	1.72/300	1602
$Cu[Al(OPr^t)(OBu^t)_3]_2$	Green solid	150/0.5*	—	1.74/300	1230 (benzene) 1490 (Nujol)

* Sublimed.

investigations carried out by Singh¹⁶ in our laboratories, Ni[Al(OMe)₂]₂ shows an electronic spectrum fully characteristic of octahedral geometry for nickel. Ni[Al(OEt)₂]₂ and Ni[Al(OPrⁱ)₂]₂, on the other hand, show increasing proportions of tetrahedral nickel species in equilibrium with octahedral forms. The effects of steric factors on this type of equilibrium can be discerned in a finer difference, i.e., the spectrum of Ni[Al(OEt)₂]₂ in ethanol shows a complete shift to octahedral species whereas for Ni[Al(OPrⁱ)₂]₂ in isopropanol, this type of shift is only partial and a stronger donor molecule like pyridine only is able to shift the same fully to the octahedral form.

Detailed physico-chemical measurements (volatility, molecular association, electronic and esr spectra as well as magnetic moments at varying temperatures) have been carried out on all the bimetallic alkoxydes and products derived from them. For brevity, only a few illustrative physical data for some typical bimetallic alkoxydes of later '3d' transition metals with aluminium and their mixed derivatives are given in Table 5. Investigations are now being extended to the bimetallic systems consisting of the above transition elements with new ligands like [Ga(OR)₂]⁻; [Zr₂(OPrⁱ)₂]⁻; [Hf₂(OPrⁱ)₂]⁻; [Nb(OR)₂]⁻ and [Ta(OR)₂]⁻.

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